

STAMPEDE/STRATOSPHERE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

STAMPEDE CLINICAL TRIAL APPROVALS

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STRATOSPHERE PROTOCOL APPROVALS

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Transcriptome analysis and association with outcome in "Abiraterone comparison"

MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL

Tel: +44 (0)20 7670 4798
Fax: +44 (0)20 7670 4818
Email: mrcctu.stampede@ucl.ac.uk

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Contacts
Emily Grist
Peter Dutey
Louise Brown

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Expansion
Abi	Abiraterone
ADT	Androgen-deprivation therapy
AR	Androgen Receptor
BI	Basal Immune
BN	Basal Neuroendocrine
CI	Confidence interval
CRF	Case Report Form
CTU	Clinical Trials Unit
DAB	Dual Androgen Blockade
DAB	Dual Androgen Blockade (previously Maximum Androgen Blockade [MAB])
FFS	Failure-free survival
GRID	Genomics Resource Information Database
HR	Hazard ratio
IDMC	Independent Data Monitoring Committee
ITT	Intention-to-treat
KM	Kaplan-Meier
LD	Luminal Differentiated
LHRH	Luteinising hormone-releasing hormone
LP	Luminal Proliferating
M0	Non-metastatic
M1	Metastatic
MAMS	Multi-arm multi-stage
MFS	Metastasis Free Survival
MPFS	Metastatic progression-free survival
MRC	Medical Research Council
N+	Lymph node-positive
N0	Lymph node-negative
NX	Lymph node stage unknown
NCCN	National Comprehensive Cancer Network
NSAID	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
ONS	Office of National Statistics
OS	Overall survival
PCa	Prostate cancer
PCSS	Prostate Cancer Specific Survival
PFS	Progression Free Survival
PIS	Patient Information Sheet
PSA	Prostate specific antigen
q6wk	Every 6 weeks
q12wk	Every 12 weeks
q6m	Every 6 months
QC	Quality Control
QL	Quality of Life
rPFS	Radiological progression-free survival
RT	Radiotherapy
RTOG	Radiation Therapy Oncology Group
SAE	Serious adverse event
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SMF	Statistical Master file
SOC	Standard-of-care
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures

SRE	Skeletal Related Event
tE2	Transdermal oestradiol
TMG	Trial Management Group
TSC	Trial Steering Committee
WHO PS	WHO Performance Status
ZA	Zoledronic acid

1 BACKGROUND AND DESIGN

1.1 TRIAL SUMMARY

This section gives a brief summary of the STAMPEDE trial, including the trial aims/objectives; treatment/randomisation arms; main outcomes; and the patient eligibility criteria.

Full details of the background to the trial and its design are presented within the current, activated version of the protocol (Version 23.0; 05-Oct-2021).

STAMPEDE is a multi-centre, platform protocol, including a number of randomised controlled trials. It recruits patients with locally advanced (M0) or metastatic (M1) prostate cancer who are starting long-term androgen-deprivation therapy (ADT) for the first time. Patients can have either newly-diagnosed disease or have been previously treated with radical radiotherapy or surgery but now have a rising prostate specific antigen (PSA). Further details on eligibility can be found in **Section 2.4**.

The trial uses multi-arm, multi-stage (MAMS) methods to simultaneously assess a number of different research treatments. The trial aims to assess the effects of adding one or two approaches to the standard-of-care (SOC).

The investigational agents to date are:

- a. A bisphosphonate, zoledronic acid
- b. A cytotoxic chemotherapeutic agent, docetaxel
- c. A cyclooxygenase (Cox-2) inhibitor, celecoxib
- d. A CYP-17 inhibitor, abiraterone
- e. Radiotherapy to the prostate amongst newly-diagnosed M1 patients only
- f. An androgen receptor signalling inhibitor, enzalutamide
- g. Metformin
- h. Transdermal oestradiol (tE2)

Patients on the control arm receive the standard-of-care; the research arms have this standard supplemented with other potential treatments, except for patients allocated to the tE2 arm who receive transdermal oestradiol in place of standard hormone treatment.

The standard-of-care is based on ADT, achieved through the use of luteinising hormone-releasing hormone (LHRH) analogues or antagonists, Dual Androgen Blockade (DAB: long-term anti-androgens in combination with LHRH agonist) or bilateral orchidectomy according to local practice (bicalutamide for non-metastatic (M0) patients was allowed in some early versions of the Protocol). This standard-of-care is also the backbone of therapy for the research arms.

Standard-of-care radiotherapy (RT) was mandated for all N0M0 patients and encouraged for N+M0 patients (unless contraindicated). RT to the prostate was permitted for M1 patients, too, although whilst the M1|RT

research Arm H was recruiting, radiotherapy was not permitted as SOC for newly-diagnosed M1 patients and should only be received through allocation to Arm H for patients corresponding to this sub-set.

1.2 COMPARISONS

A research comparison is defined by those patients allocated to the research arm, along with the corresponding contemporaneously randomised, eligible control arm patients. See **Table 1** for the definition of each research comparison within STAMPEDE to date.

Table 1: STAMPEDE research comparisons

COMPARISON NAME	INCLUDED ARMS	ELIGIBLE PATIENTS	ACCRUAL		TIME PERIOD(S)	NB
			START DATE	END DATE		
"Zoledronic acid comparison"	A, B	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	1-4	Note
"Docetaxel comparison"	A, C	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	1-4	Note
"Celecoxib comparison"	A, D	All patients	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	1	Note
"Zoledronic acid + docetaxel comparison"	A, E	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	1-4	Note
"Zoledronic acid + celecoxib comparison"	A, F	All patients	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	1	Note
"Abiraterone comparison"	A, G	All patients	15-Nov-2011	17-Jan-2014*	3-5	Note
"M1 RT comparison"	A, H	Newly-diagnosed M1 pts No contraindication to RT	22-Jan-2013	02-Sep-2016	4-9	Note
"Enzalutamide + abiraterone comparison"	A, J	All patients	29-Jul-2014	31-Mar-2016	7-9	Note
"Metformin comparison"	A, K	Non-diabetic pts	05-Sep-2016	TBD	10-TBD	---

		No contraindication to metformin				
"tE2 comparison"	A, L	<8wk anti- androgen use Maximum 4wk LHRH t'py No bilateral orchidectomy	20-Jun-2017	TBD	11-TBD	---

***Note:** One patient was manually randomised to Arm G after the cut-off of 17-Jan-2014

D, F: The celecoxib-containing arms closed accrual early due to lack of sufficient activity following their Activity Stage 2 analysis.

B, C, E: The remaining original research arms closed to recruitment having reached an acceptable sample size (based on time to analysis projections).

G: The abiraterone arm closed to recruitment having reached its revised sample size target (1800 pts) ahead of schedule.

H: The M1|RT arm closed to recruitment having reached its revised target sample size ahead of schedule.

J: The enzalutamide + abiraterone arm closed to recruitment having reached its target sample size ahead of schedule.

The trial is summarised at relevant times for this comparison in the subsequent **Figures**. The trial initially started with Arms A to F. Additional research arms have been included in the trial over time.

At the time a new research arm is activated, the strata totals in the randomisation system are reset; the team checks for imbalances before this occurs. Consideration is given to applying a small weight to the reset total to help correct this only if there is a major imbalance, defined as a difference of 12 patients or more in any given strata (NB to date this has not been required).

Figure 1: Recruiting arms from Apr-2011 to Nov-2011 (Protocol version 7.0)

Note: SOC includes mandated RT for N0M0 patients from Nov-2011

Figure 3: Recruiting arms from Jan-2013 to Mar-2013 (Protocol version 9.0)

¹ except pts with a contra-indication to RT² all suitable pts with newly diagnosed locally advanced disease should also have RT¹

Figure 4: Recruiting arms from Apr-2013 to Jan-2014 (Protocol version 10.0)

¹ except pts with a contra-indication to RT² all suitable pts with newly diagnosed locally advanced disease should also have RT¹

1.3 BIOMARKER POPULATION

Patients who consented to tissue acquisition for research in PIS versions 03-09 were eligible for inclusion in translational analyses. Analysis of these samples was as described in the STRATOSPHERE protocol V4 dated 19-Mar-2021. This SAP considers the transcriptome analysis of samples from patients randomised in the "abiraterone comparison". Further details of this subset of patients are provided in **Section 4**.

Figure 5: Activity-by-time graph showing patients contributing to the "abiraterone comparison"

Between November 2011 and January 2014, 1917 patients were randomized to ADT plus abiraterone acetate and prednisolone / prednisone (AAP) or ADT alone. M1 patients received continuous treatment until progression. M0 patients received ADT and RT and abiraterone for 2 years unless radiotherapy was omitted in which case treatment could continue to progression. Following an amendment to the STAMPEDE trial protocol (V21.0, date 20-Oct-2021) the comparison was closed to follow-up on 30-Nov-2021. This analysis will use data frozen at a later date to allow time for cleaning and entry of the data.

1.4 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

The eligibility criteria describe a broad population of patients unified by the need to start long-term ADT for the first time.

In the broadest terms, this includes patients who have had previous local therapy and now have high-risk relapse, along with patients with newly-diagnosed disease. For this comparison, this included patients with:

- High-risk locally advanced disease (at least two of: Stage T3/4 N0 M0 histologically confirmed prostate adenocarcinoma, PSA \geq 40ng/ml or Gleason sum score 8-10)
- Nodal involvement
- Metastatic disease

All patients need to give written consent to participate in additional research, be sufficiently fit and meet the full trial eligibility criteria for protocol treatment and follow-up.

For inclusion into the abiraterone translational sub-study, STAMPEDE participants must meet the following **inclusion criteria**:

1. Have consented to participate in additional research
2. Have tissue from the primary tumour (including TURP specimens) available for analyses

Participants must **not** meet any of the following **exclusion criteria**:

3. Tissue specimen collected >14 days after STAMPEDE randomisation

1.5 METHOD OF RANDOMISATION

Patients are randomised centrally using a computerised algorithm developed and maintained by the CTU. Randomisation is performed using the method of minimisation over a number of clinically important stratification factors with an additional random element. These factors are:

Randomising centre	each centre
Metastases	M0 vs M1
Nodal involvement	N0 vs NX vs N+
Age at randomisation	up to 69yrs vs 70yrs and over
WHO performance status	PS=0 vs PS=1-2
Method of ADT ¹	Orchidectomy vs LHRH agonist vs LHRH antagonist vs
Dual Androgen Blockade (DAB)	
Regular aspirin or NSAID use at baseline yes vs no	
Radiotherapy planned ²	yes vs no

¹ Method of ADT options have changed over time, from LHRH vs orchidectomy, to then include bicalutamide, then specify LHRH agonist or antagonist and more recently exclude bicalutamide but include DAB

² "Radiotherapy planned" was added as a stratification factor at the start of recruitment to Efficacy Stage I for the "original comparisons" (Mar-2008)

When implementing the additional random element of the randomisation, an 80% probability of allocation will be split between the (one or more) arms with the lowest strata totals (i.e. 80% probability of being allocated to one of the minimising arms); and the remaining 20% probability of allocation will be split between the remaining (one or more) arms. This method should provide simplicity of reporting and implementation.

1.6 ALLOCATION RATIO

The allocation ratio between the control arm and research arm in the “abiraterone comparison” for comparison-eligible patients was equal, i.e. allocation ratio 1:1.

1.7 JUSTIFICATION FOR TRANSCRIPTOME ASSESSMENT

Biomarkers to predict outcome or to stratify patients to more personalized treatments are used in oncology, and transcriptomic signatures are a type used in breast cancer. MammaPrint¹ and OncotypeDx² have been prospectively tested in clinical trials^{3,4} and found to predict outcome more accurately than clinical features alone. OncotypeDx is recommended to guide the use of adjuvant chemotherapy. Prosigna, which is based on the PAM50 group of genes, is prognostic for risk of disease recurrence⁵.

With multiple new treatments approved and in development for HSPC⁶⁻¹², there is an urgent need to stratify patients for specific treatment paradigms. DNA and protein biomarkers are being tested and their analysis in the context of the STAMPEDE trial is described elsewhere. The test performed by Decipher/Veracyte is an analytically validated test performed in a clinical level lab that has a failure rate <25% based on prior studies with similar sampling. Analysis in CHARTED also supports that selected transcriptomic signatures associate with outcome in patients treated with ADT or ADT with docetaxel.

2 OUTCOME MEASURES

The planned translational analyses will focus on Overall Survival (OS, time from randomisation to death from any cause).

Full definitions of these and other secondary outcomes considered in this analysis plan are included in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Definitions of each outcome measure with censoring criteria

TERM	DEFINITION
Overall survival (OS)	Time from randomisation until date of death from any cause from a Death CRF (Form 12). For surviving patients, censor date 1 is used. If record linkage to Civil Registrations of Death is successful, the registered date of death is used. For surviving patients, censor date 2 is used.
Metastases-Free Survival (MFS)	Time from randomisation until first of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiologically-confirmed distant metastases • Death from any cause For patients who have not had an event, censor date 2 is used (see below).
Failure-free Survival (FFS)	Time from randomisation until first of the following events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biochemical failure (as defined in protocol) • Local progression • Lymph node progression • Distant metastases • Skeletal Related Event (where confirmed disease progression) • Death from prostate cancer For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used (see below). If a suspicious event is reported for any of local progression, lymph node progression, distant metastases progression this will be counted as a FFS event.
Progression-free Survival (PFS)	Time from randomisation until first of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local progression • Lymph node progression • Distant metastases • Skeletal Related Event (where confirmed disease progression) • Death from prostate cancer For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used (see below). If a suspicious event is reported for any of local progression, lymph node progression, distant metastases progression this will be counted as a PFS event.
Metastatic Progression-Free Survival (MPFS)	Time from randomisation until first of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distant metastases • Skeletal Related Event (where confirmed disease progression) • Death from prostate cancer For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used (see below). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a suspicious event is reported for distant metastases progression this will be counted as a MPFS event.
Prostate cancer-specific survival	Time from randomisation until death from prostate cancer (see below). For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used.
Death from prostate cancer	An automated process assigns either PCa or non-PCa as cause of death using the following rules, based on information collected on CRFs:

	Rule	Cause of death
	1 Primary cause of death is PCa and no secondary causes are reported; progression event prior to death; no evidence of another cancer as an SAE 2 Primary cause of death is pneumonia and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death 3 Primary cause of death is neutropenic sepsis and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death 4 Primary cause of death is carcinomatosis and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death 5 Death is reported as caused by PCa treatment; progression event prior to death 8 Site reports on Death CRF (version 13.0+) that responsible consultant considers death predominantly caused by PCa or protocol research / standard-of-care treatment	PCa PCa PCa PCa PCa PCa
	6 Primary cause of death is other primary cancer, and is confirmed by SAE report 7 Primary cause of death is cardiovascular disease; PCa not listed as secondary cause of death 9 Site reports on Death CRF (version 13.0+) that responsible consultant considers death predominantly caused by cardiovascular disease or other condition	Non-PCa Non-PCa Non-PCa
	<p>In participants successfully linked to Civil Registrations of Deaths, a death where the underlying cause is coded as any of the following ICD10 codes will be considered a PCa death:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C61 Malignant neoplasm of prostate - C77 Secondary and unspecified malignant neoplasm of lymph nodes - C78 Secondary malignant neoplasm of respiratory and digestive organs - C79 Secondary malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified sites - C80 Malignant neoplasm, without specification of site 	
Censor date 1	<p>Date taken from the latest of the relevant variables defined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of randomisation (Form 1) • BMD assessment date (scan, blood sample, urine sample) • Date of treatment cycle (as taken from the bisphosphonate, docetaxel; Forms 4, 5, 6) • Date bloods taken (as taken from the bisphosphonate Forms 4, 5) • Date of last SOC docetaxel cycle (Form 21) • Date of any treatment action (Forms 7, 7B, 7C, 7D) • Date of any tE2 treatment action for Arm L patients (Form 25) • Date of tests recorded on hormone results log for Arm L patients (Form 24) • Dates reported on the Follow-up CRF (including date of PSA tests, date of any surgical interventions, date of any SRE, date of any metabolic or cardiovascular event; Forms 7, 7A) • Date of any reported progression event (Form 8) • Date additional treatment started or stopped (Forms 8, 8A) • Date of first/last RT fraction (Form 9A) • Date of late RT toxicity assessment (Form 10) • Date HT/research treatment ended (Form 11) • SAE date (onset, resolved, recent HT or trial treatment administration, start/end date of other treatment, test date) (Form 14) • Date of palliative RT fraction (Form 19) 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date blood or saliva sample obtained as reported on the pathology form (Form 18) • Date of co-enrolment to another trial (Form 15) • Date trial participation ended (Form 20) • Date last known alive (Form 7 from Version 13.0) • Date of death (Censoring date only for outcomes other than overall survival and disease-specific survival; Form 12) <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dates from the QoL forms are no longer used as a censor date as these are completed by the patient and cannot be queried for errors. • Dates of form completion are no longer used as the CRF may have been completed retrospectively. • Any date pre-randomisation is ignored within the calculation. <p>Unusual dates which have not yet been resolved or dates after the ending of follow-up for the "abiraterone comparison" on 30-Nov-2021 will be ignored for the purposes of calculating this censor date.</p>
<p>Censor date 2 for MFS outcome measure</p>	<p>Date taken from the latest of the relevant variables defined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of randomisation (Form 1) • Date of assessment on the Follow-up CRF (unless recorded as a missed visit; Form 7) • Date of any reported progression event (If type of progression not included as event; Form 8) <p>Unusual dates which have not yet been resolved or dates after the ending of follow-up for the "abiraterone comparison" on 30-Nov-2021 will be ignored for the purposes of calculating this censor date.</p>
<p>Censor date 3</p>	<p>For patients successfully linked to Civil Registrations of Deaths, a censoring date will be set as 4 weeks before the data transfer, depending on what the data provider advises.</p>

3 DATA COLLECTION AND PROCESSING

3.1 CASE REPORT FORMS AND VARIABLES

Full details of data collection and timings are described in the current trial protocol.

A copy of the Case Report Forms (CRFs) and Quality of Life (QL) questionnaires are presented in the Statistical Master File and the Trial Master File. Details of the variables, and any corresponding validations, are presented in the metadata which forms part of the Trial Master File.

3.2 DATA COMPLETION SCHEDULE FOR BASELINE, TREATMENT & FOLLOW-UP

The following table gives detail around the expected timing of those scheduled CRFs. Please note that detail has been removed for treatment forms relating specifically those to research arms which have reported their formal final efficacy analysis; please see the SAP version 1.0 for detail of these timings.

Table 3: Timings for completion of scheduled CRFs

TIMING OF ASSESSMENT		BASELINE		TREATMENT		OUTCOMES		FREQ
		N RAND	PRE-TRT	RT	SOC Doc	FOLLOW-UP	QL HE	
Yr 0	Wk 0	all	all				all	
	Wk 6					all	all	q6wk
	Wk 12			M1: A H		all	all	
	Wk 18				all	all	all	
	Wk 24				all	all	all	
	Wk 36					all	all	q12wk
	Wk 48			M0: A B C E G J K L		all	all	
	Wk 60					all	all	
	Wk 72					all	all	
	Wk 84					all	all	
	Wk 96					all	all	
Yr 2	Month 24					all	all	q6m
	Month 30					all	all	
Yr 3	Month 36					all	all	
	Month 42					all	all	
Yr 4	Month 48					all	all	
Yr 5	Month 60					all	all	
Yr 6+						all	all	q12m

Key: all = Arms A-L

A = SOC alone

G = SOC + abiraterone

H = SOC + M1 research RT to the prostate

J = SOC + enzalutamide + abiraterone

K = SOC + metformin

L = tE2 Text with a ~~strike through~~ indicates form no longer relevant

Note:

Pre-Trt assessment includes the following CRFs: baseline, cardiovascular, bone density risk factor questionnaire (for patients randomised from Protocol v6.0; Jul-2009).

QL & HE data were collected for the first 700 patients randomised and then for all patients randomised from Protocol v8.0 onwards (Nov-2011) who opt-in.

QL & HE data is collected until disease progression.

RT forms were not required for M0 patients on Arms D & F as they closed to recruitment prior to RT being mandated within N0M0 standard-of-care.

SOC Doc forms are required for all patients randomised from 17-Dec-2015, when the change in SOC to permit upfront docetaxel use was implemented, and for any patients randomised before this date and receiving upfront docetaxel.

3.3 DATA COMPLETION SCHEDULE FOR OTHER 'NON-SCHEDULED' CRFS

The following CRFs should be completed as required:

- Hormone therapy log (All Arms)
- Abiraterone & enzalutamide treatment log (Arms G & J)
- Metformin treatment log (Arm K)
- Transdermal oestradiol treatment log (Arm L)
- Hormone results log (Arm L)
- Toxicity form (All Arms)
- RT acute toxicity form (All Arms, pts who received RT only)
- Progression log (All Arms)
- Additional treatment log (All Arms)
- Saliva pathology form (All Arms)
- Blood form (All Arms)
- SAE form (All Arms)
- End of research treatment form (Research Arms only)
- Co-enrolment form (All Arms)
- Death form (All Arms)

For all CRFs, details of associated timings and requirements are given within their guidance notes.

3.4 CRFS NO LONGER REQUIRED

There are several CRFs which, over the time of the trial, have been replaced by an updated CRF, for which data collection has moved to another CRF, or which are no longer required.

Such CRFs include:

- Late radiotherapy toxicity CRF
- Details of RTOG late side-effects have been collected on the follow-up CRF from Jan-2013
- Withdrawal CRF
- Replaced by the end of trial participation CRF; discontinued from Sep-2016

- Hormone therapy and abiraterone & enzalutamide treatment CRFs
- Replaced by logs from Protocol version 15.0 (Sep-2016)
- Additional treatment update CRF
- Replaced by a log, linked to the progression CRF from Protocol version 15.0 (Sep-2016)
- Palliative radiotherapy
- No longer of interest as radiotherapy for progression should be reported on the additional treatment log (discontinued from Sep-2016)
- Bone mineral density (BMD) sub-study
- Sub-study discontinued from Protocol version 8.0 (Sep-2011).

3.5 EXTERNAL DISEASE VOLUME DATA

In 2018, bone scans were collected from selected patients by the team in Manchester with a view to defining patients according to metastatic involvement i.e. high or low volume like CHARTED and high or low risk like LATITUDE. These data will be incorporated into the analysis where specified using a finalised copy of the volume classification dataset saved by the MRC CTU.

4 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

4.1 AIMS

- a) In patients with advanced prostate cancer, confirm association between transcriptomic sub-types and benefit from intensified hormone treatment on clinical outcomes
- b) To identify poor prognostic molecular sub-types that derive limited benefit from addition of abiraterone to ADT and require prioritization for additional or alternative treatments
- c) To identify molecular sub-types that do not derive benefit from addition of abiraterone as they have excellent outcomes with ADT alone
- d) In patients with advanced prostate cancer, test prognostic performance of biomarkers for OS.

4.2 PATIENT COHORT

A total of 1465 patients in the “abiraterone comparison” consented to tissue biomarker analysis. All analyses described in this document will be performed on a single sample per patient. To select a single sample from those with multiple tumor expression profiles, the following hierarchical selection criteria is used (moving to the next step of the hierarchy if there are ties in the criteria among multiple samples):

1. Sample(s) with the highest primary tissue Gleason pattern based on Decipher pathology review
2. Sample(s) with the highest secondary tissue Gleason pattern based on Decipher pathology review
3. Sample(s) with the longest tumor length (mm)
4. Sample(s) with the highest microarray percent positive probes above background

Samples from 794 patients have passed microarray quality control (QC) metrics. Selected clinical features of the biomarker population (n=781) were compared with those from the intention to treat population (ITT, n=1917) and found the biomarker population to be representative of the overall ITT population, enabling generalization of our findings to the cohort as a whole (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Comparison of the main clinical features of the biomarker population used in this analysis (n=794) with the intention to treat population recruited in the trial (n=1917)

Characteristic	M0		M1	
	Microarray cohort N = 401 ¹	Overall N = 914 ¹	Microarray cohort N = 393 ¹	Overall N = 1,003 ¹
Treatment arm				
A = ADT	208 (52%)	455 (50%)	211 (54%)	502 (50%)
G= ADT and abiraterone	193 (48%)	459 (50%)	182 (46%)	501 (50%)
Age				
Under 70 years	233 (58%)	547 (60%)	250 (64%)	651 (65%)
70 years and over	168 (42%)	367 (40%)	143 (36%)	352 (35%)
Disease burden				
M0 Node-negative	246 (61%)	530 (58%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
M0 Node-positive	155 (39%)	383 (42%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
M1 Low-volume metastases	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	159 (43%)	405 (44%)
M1 High-volume metastases	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	215 (57%)	506 (56%)
Unknown	0	1	19	92
Local Grade Group				
1-2	53 (13%)	108 (12%)	36 (9.3%)	95 (9.8%)
3	46 (11%)	106 (12%)	50 (13%)	139 (14%)
4	106 (26%)	231 (25%)	89 (23%)	224 (23%)
5	196 (49%)	466 (51%)	214 (55%)	514 (53%)
Unknown	0	3	4	31
T stage				
T0-T2	29 (7.3%)	69 (7.6%)	45 (12%)	107 (12%)
T3	333 (84%)	746 (83%)	229 (62%)	559 (61%)
T4	35 (8.8%)	88 (9.7%)	95 (26%)	255 (28%)
Unknown	4	11	24	82
Baseline PSA				
0-49	234 (58%)	564 (62%)	136 (35%)	365 (36%)
50-199	137 (34%)	280 (31%)	122 (31%)	289 (29%)
200-999	29 (7.2%)	67 (7.3%)	85 (22%)	235 (23%)
1,000 and over	1 (0.2%)	3 (0.3%)	50 (13%)	114 (11%)

¹n (%)

4.3 OUTCOME MEASUREMENTS

As defined in Section 3, the outcome measures used for primary and secondary outcomes in our study can be found in **Table 5**.

Table 5: Summary of primary and secondary outcomes used in this study for each cohort

Cohort	Primary outcomes	Secondary outcomes
M0 + M1	OS	PCSS PFS
M1	OS	FFS PCSS PFS
M0	OS	MFS FFS PCSS PFS

Approximate event counts for the biomarker population can be found in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Total sample size and event counts for the endpoints considered for cohorts in Table 5

	M0	M1	All
Biomarker population	401	393	794
OS	135	280	415

4.4 SIGNATURES TO BE TESTED

Our primary objectives (outlined explicitly in the next section) will explore the relationship between these endpoints and the following four genomic signatures:

- **AR-activity (AR-A):** a score measuring the transcriptional activity of the androgen receptor (AR) based on the expression of downstream targets. Patients with low AR activity (AR-A of 11 or less) are at a higher risk of developing rapid metastasis and may fail ADT therapy faster¹⁴

- **PAM50:** a basal/luminal subtyping model originally developed for invasive breast cancer but adapted for prostate cancer¹⁵. Due to the relative sparsity of Luminal A tumor subtype calls (**Table 7**), the Luminal A class calls will be excluded in the analysis of the primary objectives.
- **PSC:** A recently developed prostate specific 'PAM50 version 2' model (Wiener et al., AUA 2022). A multinomial subtyping classifier that predicts one of four cancer subtypes: basal immune (BI), basal neuroendocrine-like (BN), luminal differentiated (LD), and luminal proliferating (LP). Due to the relative sparsity of luminal differentiated and basal neuroendocrine-like tumor subtype calls (**Table 7**), they will be excluded in the analysis of the primary objectives.
- **Decipher v1.1:** the commercially available Decipher Test using 22 probe sets in a GLMnet model^{16,17}. Decipher scores range from zero to one, with higher scores indicating a worse prognosis¹⁸. We will analyze the continuous Decipher score and dichotomised at the median value of the metastatic cohort in the primary and secondary objectives..

Due to sample age and quality, the PSC subtyping model classifies a disproportionate number of samples as basal neuroendocrine-like. To correct this, a quantile-matched version of PSC will be provided for analysis. The subset of the Decipher 'GRID' cohort (100,547 samples) classified as NCCN very high risk (1,412 samples) will be used as the reference population. The expression data of the STAMPEDE biomarker analysis cohort will be quantile matched to those from the reference population and PSC will be calculated on the matched expression data. While no quantile matching will be performed for AR-A or PAM50 in the primary analysis, a similar process will be followed to provide quantile-matched versions for use in the secondary analysis. The class call distributions for these four signatures in the M0 and M1 cohorts are given in **Table 7**.

In exploratory analyses (outlined explicitly in **Section 5.7**), we will also explore signatures available through the Genomics Resource Information Database (GRID), containing a library of >400 locked gene expression signatures.

Table 7: Prevalence for class call distributions for Decipher, AR-A, PAM50, and PSC by metastatic stage in AG biomarker cohort (n=794)

		M0	M1
AR-A (not QQ normalised)	Average AR Activity	262 (65%)	183 (47%)
	Lower AR Activity	139 (35%)	210 (53%)
PAM50 (not QQ normalised)	Luminal A	8 (2%)	8 (2%)
	Luminal B	175 (44%)	180 (46%)
	Basal	218 (54%)	205 (52%)
PSC	Luminal Differentiated (LD)	32 (8%)	13 (3%)
	Luminal Proliferating (LP)	128 (32%)	131 (33%)
	Basal Immune (BI)	212 (53%)	214 (54%)
	Basal Neuroendocrine-Like (BN)	29 (7%)	35 (9%)
Decipher	Low	83 (21%)	37 (9%)
	Intermediate	63 (16%)	50 (13%)
	High	255 (64%)	306 (78%)

4.5 PRIMARY OBJECTIVES

Our primary objectives are to test the ability of AR-A, PAM50, PSC and Decipher to predict the treatment effect of abiraterone for OS. The target of inference for predictive hypotheses will be the interaction effect between the indicated marker and treatment arm in adjusted Cox proportional hazards models for overall survival in the M0+M1 cohort for AR-A, PAM50 and PSC, and in M0 and M1 cohorts separately for Decipher (specified as both a continuous and a binary variable). The target of inference for prognostic hypotheses will be the main effect associated with Decipher score (specified as both a continuous and a binary variable) in univariable and multivariable Cox Proportional Hazards models for OS in the M0 and M1 cohorts individually.

Sensitivity Analyses:

A sensitivity analysis will report results of the primary analysis after exclusion of patients who had tissue collected after initiation of therapy.

4.6 SECONDARY OBJECTIVES

Our secondary objective is to estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of the signatures listed below for each of the primary and secondary endpoints outlined in **Table 5**. For prognostic effects, the targets of inference will be the main effects associated with each signature derived from univariable and multivariable adjusted Cox proportional hazard models. For predictive effects, the targets of inference will be the interaction effect(s) between the indicated signature and treatment arm derived from adjusted Cox proportional hazard models. The signatures under consideration are as follows:

- AR-A (Binary): Low (AR-A of 11 or less) vs. Average (AR-A > 11) AR activity
- AR-A (Continuous): Continuous AR-A score

- AR-A (Quantile-Matched Binary): Low (AR-A of 11 or less) vs. Average (AR-A > 11) AR activity after quantile-matching the genes used in the AR-A score calculation
- PSC (Binary): Luminal Proliferating vs Basal Immune
- PAM50 (Binary): Basal vs. Luminal B
- PAM50 (Quantile-Matched Binary): Basal vs. Luminal B after quantile-matching the genes used in the PAM50 class call calculation
- Decipher (Continuous): Continuous Decipher score
- Decipher (Binary): Low (Decipher \leq 0.80) vs. High (Decipher > 0.80) Risk

These analyses will be conducted in the M0 and M1 cohorts separately .

4.7 EXPLORATORY OBJECTIVES

Exploratory Objective 1: Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of other GRID signatures (e.g., neuroendocrine models, RB loss, radiation resistance, radiotherapy benefit, tumor immune microenvironment) on OS in the M0 and M1 cohorts.

Exploratory Objective 2: Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of other GRID signatures for the endpoints and cohorts specified in the **Secondary Aims**.

Exploratory Objective 3: Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of Decipher, PAM50, AR-A, PSC, and other GRID signatures for the endpoints specified in the **Secondary Aims** stratified by nodal status (positive and negative) in the M0 cohort and volume (low and high) in the M1 cohort.

Exploratory Objective 4: Estimate effects similar to those in Exploratory Objective 3 in the M0, M1, and combined M0/M1 cohorts, stratified by Decipher, PAM50, and AR-A class calls. Specifically, in the M0, M1, and combined M0/M1 cohorts separately:

- Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of PAM50, AR-A, and PSC within the Decipher High and Decipher Low-Intermediate Risk groups.
- Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of AR-A, PSC, and Decipher within the PAM50 Luminal and Basal subtype groups.
- Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of PAM50, PSC, and Decipher within the AR-A Low and High activity groups.
- Estimate the predictive and prognostic effects of PAM50, AR-A, and Decipher within each of the subtype groups defined by PSC.

4.8 METHODS

Cox proportional hazards models will be used to model the association between a signature and the hazard of the outcome of interest and, for evaluation of predictive ability, interaction between the signature and the effect of allocation to research abiraterone compared to SOC. The validity of the proportional hazards assumption will be tested using scaled Schoenfeld residuals and the Grambsch-Therneau test. Where non-proportional hazards appear to be present, alternative methods such as flexible parametric modelling will be considered.

For testing of prognostic hypotheses, multivariable models including as covariates the signature of interest, indicator of treatment allocation and the following adjustment variables will be fitted: age at randomization (years, continuous), WHO performance status (0 vs 1-2), regular aspirin or NSAID use (no vs yes), serum PSA prior to start of ADT and within 6 months of randomisation (continuous, log-transformed), Gleason score as assessed by the local pathologist (categorical, ≤ 6 ; 7; ≥ 8), nodal stage, tumour stage (T0-T2; T3; T4) and, in M1 participants, metastasis volume (CHAARTED low vs high). For testing of predictive hypotheses, models including as covariates the signature of interest, treatment allocation, a term (or terms) for their interaction, and the same adjustment variables will be fit. Models where the genetic signature of interest is continuous will specify this as a linear variable. Univariable hazard ratios will be reported in addition to multivariable hazard ratios to visualise the effect of confounding adjustment.

Metastasis volume is affected by data missingness, which will be investigated. In the event evidence show data are not missing completely at random, analyses will use multiple imputation with chained equations to handle missing observations for nodal stage, tumour stage and metastasis volume. Missing Gleason scores will be imputed using the dominant category.

Models will be stratified by the time periods patients were randomized to the "abiraterone comparison", as per earlier analyses. Time periods are defined by trial arms opening or closing, a change to the standard-of-care, or another fundamental aspect which may affect the patient population being randomized. Recruitment to the "abiraterone comparison" occurred across periods 3, 4 and 5. Given the limited number of patients randomised during period 4 in the analysis sample, we will combine periods 3 and 4 into a single stratum for this purpose. See **Table 8** below for further details.

Inference from these models will be derived using likelihood ratio tests, with 95% confidence intervals reported for prognostic effects / modification of treatment effects.

Table 8: Time periods within STAMPEDE up to and including closure of recruitment to the "abiraterone comparison" (accrual time periods relevant to this analysis are highlighted in yellow)

Time Period	Definition	Accrual Start Date	Accrual End Date	Co-Recruiting Research Arms
1	From the start of the trial up to the stopping of the celecoxib-containing research Arms D & F	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	B C D E F
2	Post-closure of Arms D & F up to the opening of the abiraterone research Arm G	06-Apr-2011	14-Nov-2011	B C E
3	Post-opening of Arm G up to the opening of the M1 radiotherapy research Arm H	15-Nov-2011	21-Jan-2013	B C E G
4	Post-opening of Arm H up to the closure of the remaining original research Arms B, C & E	22-Jan-2013	31-Mar-2013	B C E G H
5	Post-closure of Arms B, C & E up to the closure of abiraterone research Arm G	01-Apr-2013	17-Jan-2014*	G H
6	Post-closure of Arm G up to the opening of the enzalutamide+abiraterone research Arm J	18-Jan-2014	28-Jul-2014	H

*Note: One patient was manually randomised to Arm G after the cut-off of 17-Jan-2014

4.9 POWER CALCULATIONS (PRIMARY OBJECTIVES)

Power calculations for each hypothesis in the primary objectives were performed using the event counts for each outcome (**Table 6**) and genomic classifier call proportions (**Table 7**) via the methods outlined in Freedman¹⁹ (for prognostic power calculations with continuous covariates) and Schmoor²⁰ (for predictive power calculations with binary covariates). The significance level was set at 0.05 for predictive and prognostic hypotheses. **Table 9** shows the detectable cause-specific hazard ratios with power fixed at 80%.

Table 9: Detectable cause-specific hazard ratios for each primary objective with power fixed at 80%

Primary Objective	Classifier	Detectable interaction or ratio of hazard ratios
M0: Predictive for OS	Decipher Score (>0.8)	0.39
M1: Predictive for OS	Decipher Score (>0.8)	0.51
Full cohort: Predictive for OS	AR-A (Low vs. Average Activity)	0.58
Full cohort: Predictive for OS	PAM50 (Luminal vs. Basal)	0.58
Full cohort: Predictive for OS	PSC (Luminal P vs. Basal I)	0.56

SIGNATURES OF APPROVAL

Date: 19/03/2024**Version:** 2.0**Signatures**

Name	Trial Role	Signature	Date
Gert Attard	Chair, Biological Research Group, STAMPEDE Chief Investigator, STRATOSPHERE protocol		20-Mar-2024
Emily Grist	Clinical Research Fellow		20-Mar-2024
Louise Brown	Project Lead		20-Mar-2024
Peter Dutey	Senior statistician		20-Mar-2024
Nick James	Chief Investigator, STAMPEDE trial*		20-Mar-2024
Elai Davicioni	Chief Project Scientist, Veracyte		20-Mar-2024

*On behalf of the STAMPEDE Trial Management Group

This SAP was written by James A Proudfoot Chris Brawley and Marina Parry with input from Louise Brown, Elai Davicioni, Darby JS Thompson, Vinnie YT Liu, Yang Liu, Jing Huang, Gert Attard.

Reviewers: Chris Sweeney (DFCI, January 2022), Anis Hamid (University of Melbourne, January 2022), Matt Sydes (MRC CTU, March 2022)

Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
Final 2.0	19/03/2024	Peter Dutey/Emily Grist	Finalising for signatures
Draft 1.2	15/03/2024	Peter Dutey	Aligning methods for the primary objectives, updating numbers and power calculations
Draft 1.1	07/12/2023	Peter Dutey	Aligning methods with STRATOSPHERE docetaxel SAP version 2.0
Final 1.0	17/03/2022	Gert Attard	

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